

December 2023

Press release

The CST4ALL project successfully completed the Online Workshop on the Cross-Cutting Materials Challenges of Renewable Energy Technologies on November 9th, 2023. This virtual event, organised by ODTÜ-GÜNAM raised significant interest from various sectors of renewable energy technologies, with stakeholders from industry, research institutions, and universities. The event had a high interest with participation from over 150 participants.

The first part of the workshop featured a series of presentations showcasing recent advancements in concentrated solar thermal (CST), photovoltaics (PV), wind, geothermal, and biomass technologies, with a specific emphasis on the materials challenges within each sector. In the subsequent session, experts engaged in a round table discussion to delve into cross-cutting materials challenges.

The workshop successfully brought together leading experts from various renewable energy sectors. The interactive round table discussion, complemented by audience questions, effectively identified key elements of cross-cutting materials challenges across different sectors and explored potential avenues for collaborative solutions.

The main pathways within the session presentations and discussions included:

- Importance of environmentally durable and sustainable coatings to enhance optical and panel properties in a cost-effective and sustainable manner
- Similar concerns in different fields : Erosion in wind turbines is a potential collaborative research area with PV and CST to improve new coating performance
- Large-scale deployment of hybrid panels for CST and PV poses numerous challenges, although smaller-scale applications can still benefit from these approaches.
- Standardized procedures for testing and qualifying new materials across sectors is an important collaboration opportunity
- Molten-salt storage tanks in Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) systems and those in molten-salt-based nuclear reactors is another significant cross-cutting materials challenge.
- Material recycling, particularly during power plant decommissioning, presents a common materials challenge

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the European Union**

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CST4ALL Coordinator

**Deutsches Zentrum
für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V.**
in der Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft

DLR: Deutsches Zentrum fuer Luft - Und Raumfahrt EV (DE)

CST4ALL Partners

Ciemat
Centro de Investigaciones
Energéticas, Medioambientales
y Tecnológicas

CIEMAT: Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas,
Medioambientales y Tecnologicas (ES)

Italian National Agency for New Technologies,
Energy and Sustainable Economic Development

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo
sviluppo economico sostenibile (IT)

ESTELA: European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (BE)

GUNAM: Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications
(TR)

The CST4ALL project is committed to catalysing an array of hybridisation and cooperation initiatives at the interface between CST and other renewable energy technologies targeting the electricity, heat, and fuels sectors.

To stay up-to-date on CST4ALL's activities and opportunities, follow-us on:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/cst4all/>
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You can also sign-up for the **CST4ALL Newsletter** to receive updates on other project events and outputs through the following link: <https://cst4all.eu/en/4169-contact-connect>.

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